

Section Concept

for establishing a section within the association
German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)

Name

Section International Engagement

Acronym of the section

section-int

Contact persons for section setup

NFDI-Geschäftsstelle

Dr. Wilma Wolf

Wilma.Wolf@nfdi.de

NFDI-Geschäftsstelle

Rebecca Kröhler

Rebecca.Kroehler@nfdi.de

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Abstract

Internationalization as a cross-cutting topic inherent to science has been a focus of NFDI since its inception. Section Internationalization (Int) addresses the need for a coordinated approach to interacting with European and international communities. The section also aims to enable broader participation from relevant members of the NFDI community in concerted activities motivated by the association's strategy, such as the establishment of a German national EOSC node.

Section Internationalization (Int) aims to (i) support the development of a German national EOSC node, (ii) operationalize the landscape into a workflow that suggests relevant external entities for NFDI to interact with, summarize the purpose and important context of such an interaction, and identify the appropriate individuals or groups within NFDI to mediate the interaction, and (iii) develop a more generic, reusable framework for contextualizing existing European and international activities relevant to NFDI consortia and sections to help in developing and nurturing European and international interactions.

Introduction

In the last five years, the NFDI has successfully coordinated and consolidated efforts in research data infrastructure and services at the national level in Germany. Because such efforts are often embedded within a larger European and international context, many NFDI consortia and sections already interact with European and international research infrastructures such as the Research Data Alliance (RDA), the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), and European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs); European funding programs such as Horizon Europe; and other entities. Through these interactions, NFDI has already made substantial contributions to international data and metadata standards. Notably, NFDI has participated in projects fundamental to the European Open Science Cloud's (EOSC) technical infrastructure and has subsequently been selected as the future operator of a German national EOSC node.

The NFDI Director and the Consortia Assembly jointly propose a new section, Internationalization (Int), in order to establish a technical, legal, and organizational foundation to support NFDI consortia in effective outreach to European and international partners. Here, we consider internationalization as the process through which NFDI consortia and their members achieve outreach, collaboration, and communication with European and international partners (e.g., working groups, projects, organizations, funders, other stakeholders).

Internationalization has the benefits of fostering collaboration, deduplicating effort, accruing international recognition, and creating opportunities for international funding. However, it also presents sev-

eral challenges: first, interacting with larger European and international partners often requires addressing complicated and sometimes vague requirements, navigating unfamiliar bureaucracy, and understanding socio-historical context. Second, European and international collaborations, despite their importance, are often under- or unfunded, necessitating principled prioritization of in-kind contributions and careful time management. Finally, the proliferation and complexity of the landscape of institutional, national, and international entities relevant to each NFDI consortium hinders onboarding new individuals to NFDI consortia, complicates prioritizing outreach activities, and creates risk in duplication of work.

The NFDI's goals in internationalization are to coordinate and consolidate efforts with European and international partners similar to its national concept within Germany. Accordingly, the primary goals of Section Int are to directly address the previously stated challenges in internationalization by organizing information about the European and international landscapes relevant for NFDI consortia, developing tools and training materials to support NFDI consortia in internationalization, and coordinating one or more key demonstrations of internationalization. Section Int will use supporting the development and contribution of a German national EOSC node to the EOSC federation as a key task, motivated by the NFDI Directorate, as one such demonstration. Ultimately, the experience gleaned from the EOSC scenario will be used to inform other high-profile collaborations.

Goals and Success Criteria

Section Int aims to provide NFDI consortia, sections, and initiatives with a transparent, repeatable pathway to engage with and contribute to European and international research infrastructures while mitigating risks and promoting alignment with external standards. Our first two activities focus on surveying the European and international research data infrastructure landscape and supporting the deployment of a German national EOSC node (EOSC Node Germany). Our final activity focuses on operationalizing the respective context and lessons learned from the first two activities towards future internationalization activities.

Surveying the European and International Landscape

Goal The first goal is to identify existing and aspirational interactions between NFDI (on the individual, organization, and consortium level) and relevant European and international entities (e.g., working groups, projects, organizations, funders, infrastructures, and other stakeholders). We aim to contextualize each interaction with its type (e.g., collaboration, delivery of work), the actors within NFDI that mediate the interaction, the goals and benefits of the interaction, and the inputs/outputs of the interaction. For each European and international entity, we also aim to identify the data standards on which it works and activities in which it participates.

Goal The second goal is to operationalize the landscape into a workflow that suggests relevant external entities for NFDI to interact with, summarizes the purpose and important context of such an interaction, and identifies the appropriate individuals or groups within NFDI to mediate the interaction.

Success Criteria Deliver a workflow for collecting, summarizing, and prioritizing such information and the results from its application. Deliver a tool through which NFDI consortia can explore the information interactively.

Support the development of a German national EOSC node

Goal: The central goal is to support the establishment of an NFDI-operated German national EOSC node, entitled EOSC Node Germany. The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) will establish a federation of geographical, thematic, and infrastructure nodes with the aim to enable access to digital resources and services across borders and disciplines. Because NFDI is developing similar capabilities on a national level, the NFDI has the goal to not only connect suitable NFDI services via the EOSC Node Germany to the EOSC Federation but to also participate in the early development of the agenda of the EOSC Federation. This will benefit the NFDI, its consortia, and its members by increasing the visibility and availability of their services, accruing international recognition, creating opportunities for international funding, and as an early contributor, enabling NFDI to shape the EOSC agenda to the needs of the scientific communities represented in NFDI.

Because this is a complicated task, Section Int will support the further implementation of the node by planning and coordinating with all stakeholders. It will serve as a point of contact for all matters concerning the establishment of the EOSC Node Germany and will give the NFDI community the possibility to directly support the development of the node.

Based on the developmental timeline for EOSC pilot nodes, two service-specific aims can be defined: First, by October 2026 a prototype of the node needs to be operational with a sandbox environment. In addition, the organizational and legal framework for the operation of the node needs to be completed as well. Second, by October 2027 the node needs to be in productive use. Parallel to these aims, a NFDI needs to develop a common interpretation of the EOSC Federation Handbook and implementation guidelines for entities who would like to onboard their services to the EOSC Node Germany.

Success Criteria: Establish the section as the nexus of coordination for EOSC-related tasks throughout NFDI consortia, sections, and partners. Publish materials such as an EOSC roadmap and onboarding workflow that support the interactions between internal partners and the envisioned EOSC Node Germany, and support the partners working on the node's direct implementation.

Continuation of Internationalization and Outreach

Goal: While Section Int frames EOSC as its primary demonstration of internationalization, our secondary goal is to collect experiences and lessons learned from supporting the deployment of EOSC Node Germany and operationalize them in a reusable framework that supports NFDI consortia in developing and nurturing European and international interactions. We then aim to support the NFDI consortia in this effort, specifically identifying and highlighting a second and subsequent major demonstrations following EOSC (e.g., interactions between ELIXIR and the life/natural sciences NFDI consortia).

Success criteria: Gather insights and lessons learned from the development of EOSC Node Germany and other international collaborations involving NFDI consortia, sections, and partners. Develop a reusable framework to support NFDI consortia and sections in building and sustaining European and international partnerships.

Tasks and Structure

Section Int is structured into three tasks: T1 Surveying the European and International Landscape, T2 Supporting the Development of EOSC Node Germany, and T3 Continuation of Internationalization and Outreach.

Task 1 Surveying the European and International Landscape

Task 1.1 Develop and deploy a survey to send to each NFDI consortium that will inquire about relevant external entities (e.g., projects, organizations) and collect relevant context. Align with pre-existing vocabulary used in the *Collaborative Work in NFDI* (<https://zenodo.org/records/15880071>) document. In collaboration with **Task 2**, use EOSC and RDA as motivating examples.

Task 1.2 Send the survey to all NFDI consortia and partners. The estimated runtime is two months, during which, advertize across various communication channels to promote participation.

Task 1.3 Develop a semi-automated workflow for standardizing the survey results (e.g., to make them FAIR) and enriching them (e.g., to connect to both internal and external knowledge graphs)

Task 1.4 Develop reusable analytical workflows and produce reporting materials appropriate for NFDI stakeholders and new NFDI consortium members answering key questions. Present these reports at the NFDI Consortia Assembly meeting in October 2026 and the NFDI Scientific Senate meeting in November 2026.

Task 1.5 Repeat the activities in **Tasks 1.2-1.4** on a yearly basis and include additional year-over-year reporting.

Requirements We envision this task requires the people with experience in/aptitude for setting up a survey (specifically nocoDB), analyses and visualization, project management, and taking responsibility for the task “internationalization” in the specific consortia.

Task 2 Supporting the Development of EOSC Node Germany

Task 2.1 Subsume the EOSC Node Working Group into Section Int, which will include reorganization and summarization of previous activities, roles, identification and incorporation of new members, provisioning of new working groups, coordination with the NFDI Directorate, the emerging services of Base4NFDI, the outputs of the pilot national node activities in EOSC Beyond, and fostering an open forum for exchange with other EOSC nodes.

Task 2.2 Design an EOSC roadmap aligned to NFDI goals and EOSC requirements (e.g., from the [EOSC Federation Handbook](#)), building on previous efforts and establishing new working groups, where appropriate.

Task 2.3 Support the development of the prototype EOSC Node Germany with the structure and functionality of a national node.

Task 2.4 Develop a workflow for onboarding new services provided by NFDI consortia into the EOSC Node Germany. Define selection criteria, define a submission process, and write guidelines/documentation to support the NFDI consortia throughout.

Task 2.5 Support the transition of EOSC Node Germany from prototype into production. Support the design of the organizational and contractual framework for EOSC-compliant operation and demonstrating key NFDI-defined capabilities and services.

Requirements We envision this task requires the people with experience in/apptitude for legal expertise, project management/leadership, people who are responsible for EOSC-related topics, and project members of relevant EOSC projects.

Task 3 Continuation of Internationalization and Outreach

Task 3.1 Publish an NFDI handbook including guidelines and other materials to support NFDI consortia in prioritizing, establishing, and reporting on new external interactions. Formulate these materials with input from **Task 2** to reflect lessons learned.

Task 3.2 Identify, support, and report on other emerging key external interactions. Support the NFDI consortia, sections, and other initiatives in making a second major demonstration of internationalization following EOSC.

Governance

The governance of Section Int will follow the by-laws of the NFDI Association and the non-binding guidelines (“Leitfaden”) for NFDI Sections. However, in contrast to other sections and other activities within Section Int, there will be an additional organizational structure to govern and perform the work on EOSC Node Germany. Due to the substantial workload required to carry out the proposed tasks and high level of coordination required between Section Int, the consortia, other sections, associated bodies, external stakeholders, and experts, it is necessary to establish a Task Team that will support the establishing EOSC Node Germany (cf. the subsection *Supporting the Development of the EOSC Node Germany*). We estimate a required 18-24 person-months (PMs) distributed over two E13 and one E7 positions for an estimated total budget of 260,000 EUR/year. The positions will be organized as a staff unit within the NFDI head office of the NFDI association.

The funded work will be supervised by a steering committee (SC) comprising a chair and three other individuals elected by voting members of Section Int, that are independent from the speaker(s) of the section. Before the voting the members of the steering committee confirm a commitment of five hours per week on the development of the project. The chair of the SC will be responsible for overall management, while each of the other three other members will be assigned to one of the following topics: technical, legal, and financial clarifications that are necessary during the establishment of EOSC Node Germany.

Timeline and Milestones

The following chart gives an overview of the three tasks and their associated milestones within a two-year window. Notably, the EOSC task has both high demand as well as high flexibility.

Cooperation

To achieve the goals of the section and at the same time not to duplicate efforts of other sections or task forces, the section Int will work closely with the following sections, task forces, and partners in NFDI in particular:

- NFDI “Governance and Sustainability” Task Force
- BASE4NFDI

Sections

- Section Common Infrastructures (Infra)
- Section Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects (ELSA)
- Section Industry Engagement
- Section (Meta)data, Terminologies, Provenance (Metadata)
- Section Training & Education (EduTrain)

Writing-Group

In alphabetischer Reihenfolge

- Alexandra Büttner (NFDI4Culture)
- Christian Busse (NFDI4Immuno)
- Andreas Haungs (PUNCH4NFDI)
- Charles Hoyt (NFDI4Chem)
- Lukas Jansen (NFDI-Geschäftsstelle)
- Rebecca Kröhler (NFDI-Geschäftsstelle)
- Najla Rettberg (Base4NFDI)
- Nanette Reißler-Pipka (Text+)
- Ahmed Saleh (BERD@NFDI)
- Christian Schäfer-Neth (Base4NFDI)
- Thomas Schörner-Sadenius (PUNCH4NFDI)
- Hendrik Seitz-Moskaliuk (NFDI-Geschäftsstelle)
- Ulrik Stervbo (NFDI4Immuno)
- Heiko Weber (FAIRmat)
- Jos van Wezel (KIT)
- Wilma Wolf (NFDI-Geschäftsstelle)(Anhang)